

Preprocessing revisited

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Spectroscopic data (or, in general, experimental data) may be affected by several sources of variability, not all of which are of interest for the specific task the data are collected for. On the other hand, very often when chemometric tools are applied to the data, model building is based on extracting components that account for a relevant share of the variance in the predictor space so that all the sources of data variability (wanted or unwanted) will be included in the model. Accordingly, if spurious/unwanted variance is still present in the data, it can have a detrimental effect on the resulting model. To at least partially reduce or eliminate the effect of such unwanted variability, chemometric model building usually includes one or more preprocessing steps. However, the choice of the best pretreatment or combination of pretreatments to be applied to the data is not always obvious, and, in general, a trial and error procedure is followed. In the present communication, a recently proposed strategy called Sequential Preprocessing through ORThogonalization (SPORT), based on the idea that the same set of spectra, differently preprocessed, could result in a multi-block data and, accordingly, be processed through dedicated multi-block strategies, will be presented (Roger et al., 2020). It relies on the use of sequential and orthogonalized partial least squares regression (SO-PLS; Biancolillo & Næs, 2019), due to the possibility of including/excluding blocks, evaluating their incremental contribution, and identifying which matrices carry common and distinctive information. With the occasion, a recently proposed alternative to data normalization called variable sorting for normalization (VSN; Rabatel et al., 2020) will also be introduced.

Keywords: data preprocessing, sequential and orthogonalized partial least squares (SO-PLS) regression, Sequential Preprocessing through ORThogonalization (SPORT)

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